

Crowdfunding Platform for Education that Employs Smart Contract to Enhance Time Efficiency

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Abstract- This study proposes a novel way to transform the financing of education by utilizing a crowdfunding system based on utilizing blockchain technology, with the aim of enabling educational institutions, instructors, and learners alike. Our aim is to develop a decentralized environment where creative learning projects may be supported, allowing pupils who are having financial difficulties to look for assistance and supporting local schools in their requests for program and facility improvements. As the crowdfunding industry becomes more transparent and accountable, our platform encourages developers to work together to improve characteristics and capabilities of the project while utilizing Web3 technology to provide an intuitive online interface. With polygon's scalability advantage, the main aim is to evolve and develop the system's proficiency while fostering community interaction and gaining support for projects initiatives. produces the best results, cuts down on the time-consuming complexity of the processes, and creates a safe platform for institutions and students. Time-management, user-friendly, security-focused, and readily available platform. provides the most favourable result for everyone procedures according to the user's feasibility.

Keywords- Blockchain, Decentralised, Crowdfunding, Smart Contract, Polygon, Web3.

1. INTRODUCTION

Because of my restricted financial means, many students globally encounter obstacles when pursuing higher education in the modern world. As education costs grow, many young people's dreams of pursuing higher education are dashed because they cannot afford the living expenses, textbooks, and tuition required to attend college. This monetary obstacle limits prospects for both the professional and personal progress, in addition to the stifling goals.

A crowdsourcing website powered by blockchain designed exclusively for children was developed in answer to this challenge. This creative method addresses financial limitations by utilizing smart contracts and blockchain methodology. Students may participate in crowdfunding projects through our site, raising money for their education and fulfilling their aspirations of attending college. The suggested blockchain technology functions as a decentralized and dispersed digital ledger that tracks transactions across a computer network connected to the internet. It is difficult to change or distort recorded information because of its decentralization. Through the using social media and internet platforms, a large number of people may contribute modest amounts of money through crowdfunding, it's a strong instrument for funding educational initiatives.

Our methodology minimizes dependencies compared to traditional crowdfunding approaches that rely on middlemen such as banks, financial institutions, payment processors, and crowdsourcing sites. Our goal is to lower fundraising expenses and give project managers more authority over their efforts by doing away with middlemen. This simplified procedure improves crowdfunding's efficacy and efficiency for educational purposes, giving aspirant students more impacting and accessible options.

Figure 1. Process of crowdfunding.

This suggested approach can use the blockchain technology to address these problems by utilizing the unique properties of the blockchain, such as security, decentralization, and transparency. Without any need for third party, blockchain provides an immutable, decentralized database that makes transaction monitoring secure and transparent. This is very effective. According to some research on blockchain-based crowdfunding, individuals, companies, and startups may easily generate capital with the aid of crowdfunding. These studies, however, don't use crowdsourcing for educational reasons; instead, they concentrate mostly on the process. The primary drawback of that specific research report is that fundraisers are employed as middlemen in a prior study [9]. This suggested approach fixes the issue and improves the platform's functionality, making it beneficial for both investors and fundraisers. Makes the platform more secure and increase the transparency of the platform. It is the main benefit of the suggested method. User friendly approach is used in which user can find out most of the optimal result. They don't face any issues like transaction

and processing. Overall, the platform is quite good for students to increase the fund for their projects.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Data breaches may be less likely with blockchain since it is decentralized and unchangeable. Because the blockchain-based crowdfunding mechanism is decentralized, it becomes more transparent. This work makes an effort to address these current problems by utilizing a blockchain-based digital identity management system. A digital identity management system that integrates blockchain technology makes it possible to identify and take action against malevolent people. Examined on the Rinkeby Test Network, this article investigates donation-based crowdfunding with Ethereum as a framework. A number of crowdfunding campaigns can run concurrently with this technique. In-depth explanations of the Solidity-written smart contract are provided in this work. [1].

In the framework of sustainable development, this article suggests a decentralized web3 application that makes use of blockchain technology to improve the efficiency and transparency of educational donations. In order to guarantee safe and transparent transactions, the platform makes use of smart contracts and decentralized protocols. This allows contributors to monitor the use of their donations and guarantees that their money reaches the designated recipients. This essay addresses the platform's conception and execution, emphasizing its attributes and potential to revolutionize the field of charity contributions. This software program has educational potential; a demonstration and several scenarios and work cases are provided and examined. Other future study avenues are made possible by the primary results and contributions, which benefit not just the authors. [2].

The goal of this article is to examine several blockchain-based higher education programs while concentrating on the protocol utilized in this project. In order to enhance the use of technology in the field of education by utilizing the blockchain feature, it is also necessary to analyse the blockchain features that are already in use as well as the services that will be provided by ongoing educational initiatives. [3].

Previously serving as an intermediary, a crowdfunding site will now solely provide its own cryptocurrency, which it will use to facilitate transactions and exchanges. In addition to notifying everyone on the network about the initiative, fundraisers will create their own currency. Investors will purchase this cryptocurrency in order to obtain a stake in the project, but they are free to remove their investment at any moment by selling it, forfeiting their project share, or moving it to another project. This innovative and modern method of fundraising may be further enhanced by blockchain technology, which will make it more dependable and transparent. [4].

This crowdfunding website offers supporters the promise of guaranteed returns, setting it apart from other applications that only let users invest their money. In order to allow supporters to remain informed about the status of the projects being worked on by the start-ups in whom they have committed their capital, the application will further facilitate transparency between backers and start-ups. Should the project be abandoned in the interim, supporters will receive their money returned. Three distinct user kinds will be included in this multi-user application: administrators, backers, and startup users. Start-ups may be approved

for listing by admin. Startups get real-time access to the funding and project approval status. [5].

The author discusses to modernize the student loan program using blockchain and crowdsourcing to assist lessen the burden of government and consequently minimize spending. Their project proposes a decentralized crowdsourced loan network that uses the application blockchain technology, allowing investors to contribute money to support college students. Students will be able to apply for loans from investors through financial organizations with a registration on the site. When the students graduate and start working, they will have to repay the loans with interest. Students will be able to pay for their education using the proposed platform, investors will earn interest on their capital, and governments will be able to redirect the capital they provide to student loan programs into other uses. We do a complete security study and provide numerical figures to support the effectiveness of our work [6].

A smart contract is a digital version of a physical contract that is kept on a blockchain and is represented by a little computer program. You can utilize these smart contracts to put reasoning into practice. Here is a solution that makes use of smart contracts to oversee every action taken during a crowdfunding campaign. The suggested approach has been put into practice, and test networks are supporting campaigns on rinks to evaluate its different characteristics. [7].

Decentralized crowdfunding provides more accessibility, transparency, and lower fees through the use of blockchain technology. The most important feature is the instantaneous creation, viewing, and donation to crowdfunding projects over the blockchain. Connected to the blockchain, the decentralized crowdfunding site allows users to write Solidity code, pair MetaMask, communicate with smart contracts, and transmit Ethereum via the network. [8].

Conventional crowdfunding services impose processing fees on every transaction and involve middlemen. The recipient experiences diminished capital as a result. By doing away with the need for middlemen, a blockchain-based strategy reduces the amount of processing fees that are charged. Fundamentally, a blockchain is transparent, auditable, decentralized, and safe. This creates a safe environment in which beneficiaries and investors may collaborate in a sincere and regulated way. There have also been instances of bogus projects. Potential investors are intimidated by such contretemps. Smart contracts in blockchain crowdfunding can lessen these kinds of incidents. Therefore, it makes sense to consider a blockchain-based crowdfunding strategy. [9].

Upon examination of the previously suggested approach and methods, several security and authenticity-related problems are discovered. Therefore, the goal of this approach or suggested module is to address every problem and create an efficient, user-centred platform. Adopt voting procedures, blockchain technology, smart contracts, and do away with middlemen, all of which will benefit investors and campaigners. Also, in this proposed method the loan system is eliminated, totally transparent and without any rate of interest just like charity. So, this platform will very helpful for students those who want to increase funds for projects.

3. METHODOLOGY

Previous study articles and survey reports assert that systems for crowdsourcing have included blockchain technology. These techniques do have significant shortcomings, though. This article identifies and fixes these flaws in the suggested approach, outlining how to fix these issues and accomplish the objective from the viewpoint of the user. The following technique is included in the platform.

To start a campaign, campaigners, students, users, etc. first contact the platform and go through each of the guidelines. The next-stage for users is to construct their campaign and upload the relevant project information, credentials, certificates, and outcomes.

Figure 2. Proposed Methodology

An administrator then carefully goes over the certifications and papers that were turned in. The project is approved if the admin confirms all the information and finds that to be accurate. Conversely though, the campaign is cancelled and the campaigner is instantly alerted of the termination if any disparities reveal themselves throughout the verification process and cause disagreement with the information supplied. The campaign may now formally begin with the administrator's approval, allowing the campaigner to start gathering money for their initiative. During the second stage, users can visit the platform and evaluate the campaign. Users can donate money to the project if campaigners are pleased with the project specifics and inspired by the campaigner's idea. It is crucial to remember that all money is safely stored in smart contracts with limitations on withdrawals. After the voting process, only the creator is able to take money back. A key element of this procedure is the voting process, which guarantees the safe withdrawal of cash by requiring the campaigner to receive at least 51% of the votes in Favor in order to get the designated funds.

The suggested voting mechanism's efficacy greatly raises the process's overall dependability. The campaigner or creator will not be able to grab the money back if the voting mechanism is less than 51%. Following that, the users' donations will be reimbursed. This suggested that individuals are eager to participate, money to the initiative. Every preference of the system is

completely verified and safe. Any student or educational institution that is able to organize campaigns to generate money for projects, infrastructure, education, etc. is observe a campaigner in this factor. All things considered, the suggested platform is simple to use, effective, and straightforward to grasp. The preceding graphic includes every step of pair in the approach.

In this methodology we use smart contract which is effective for fund raiser and fund donors. Because it is the digital method by which a donor can donate fund and if the fund is not provided to the campaigners in any case, then it will refund to the donors. This is a main benefit of using the smart contract. Another thing is that it's safe platform for campaigners to raise the fund for their projects. When the campaign is created then several users come on platform to view the projects and their details if it is good and feasible then they can donate funds for their projects otherwise not. All the functionality can be handled by the admin or some portion can be controlled by the campaigners, but whole campaign is controlled by the campaigner also because it is created by them. The methodology is quite simple and understandable for users. So, it is the good platform for fund raisers, basically for students.

4. RESULTS

The proposed decentralised platform has result in specific manner. The platform shows how to create charity (campaign) and then it shows the separate campaign of the user after creation of campaign. User can visit on site and review the campaign and according to their choice they can fund to the campaigner. The proposed platform is quite different from the previous proposed platforms. It is noted that the proposed platform's performance is fast with relation to the others.

The proposed platform is giving the extraordinary performance, it controls the all the modules functionality according to the user's needs. It gives highly performance and reduce the time complexity of every execution processes. It reduces the users pain point and make the platform very effective. In previous proposed methods it was also the issue regarding time efficiency. That problem resolved by our proposed platform. The user involvement of the platform is high as related to the others. The loading time of the pages is reduced and maintain the sequence of the pages according to minimize the loading time of the pages and also increase the transparency of the crated campaign. The platform gives the different modules which help the campaigners to know the functionality of the platform. The proposed platform also reduces the difficulties of the campaign creation anyone can create campaign without facing any difficulties. Figure 3 shows the performance efficiency of all the operations in contrast of time taken to process the complete operational task.

Figure 3: Performance efficiency of the operations

Figure 3 estimates how long it took by the all operations to execute the particular operation. It clears the ability of the system. As contrast to others this particular platform gives high reputed performance as contrast with another platforms. Overall, it improves all the performance related issues. Platform resolves following issues:

1.Transaction issue: It improves the transaction area and improve its efficiency, makes faster donation to the campaign, without facing any issues.

2. Reduce processing time: The proposed method increases the efficiency and reduce the accent of the process executing at all intervals. Reduce the user's facing issues, they can find easily accessible features.

3. Reduce security concerns: Maintains user's information secure by using blockchain technology, in previous proposed methods the security is the principal issue but our platform reduces this issue and increase the security of the campaign and secure the user's data effectively. There is no chance to steal the user's information.

The general perspective of the proposed decentralised platform is quite good and beneficial for students and other users, it is safe to use without any terror. All the fund will go to the campaigner wallet which is secured by the smart contract. It makes the transparency between the donor and the receiver on the platform that is among the advantages of this platform. According to the blockchain technology the proposed method is very effective and useful for the students and other institutions. Generally, our platform reduces almost all the

functionality related issues. It increases the user involvement and make transparency of the platform for both campaigners and the donors. Focusses and resolve the time efficiency, security, transparency, data security and other processes or operations.

CONCLUSION

Among the innovations that has made it easier for new platforms to assist companies and organizations in raising money through conventional ways is crowdfunding. Our primary objective is to assist gifted kids who want to pursue further education yet are not able to do so due to financial limitations. Through the website, kids from disadvantaged backgrounds may raise money for their education. Fundraisers will showcase their project ideas and any associated paperwork on this platform, which should be available to all team members. By using blockchain technology in crowdfunding, less paperwork would be required and every transaction will be recorded, which will increase the project idea's credibility and trustworthiness. Documents will also be readily available and safe. Using blockchain technology has several benefits, one of which is the ability for all funders to follow a project's daily development. More complex smart contracts may be developed in the future to manage a larger variety of crowdfunding situations, including reward-based, debt, and equity crowdfunding. After implementing our platform gives the optimal result and reduce the time complexity of the operations and make secure platform for the students and institutions. Easily accessible, security focussed, user friendly and time managing platform. Gives the optimal result of all the operations in contrast of user's feasibility.

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